

AN INTEGRATED ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FRAMEWORK FOR PREDICTING POSTOPERATIVE SEPSIS AND WOUND INFECTIONS IN DIABETIC PATIENTS USING RANDOM FOREST ALGORITHM

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Abstract

Patients with type 2 diabetes have higher risk of post operative complications i.e. surgical wound infections and sepsis. If not treated with proper treatment that may lead to prolonged hospitalization and also increase morbidity rate. Identification of high risk patients diabetic patients can improve surgical outcomes and optimize clinical management.

This study aim to design and develop a model based on random forest algorithm to predict the high risk patients with post operative complications.

A retrospective analysis was conducted using the dataset collected from local hospitals of hyderabad. The dataset developed included demographic information, laboratory indicators and surgical characteristics i.e. procedure specialty, operative duration and anesthesia type. The dataset was divided into 80/20 ratio in which 80% was for training set and 20% was reserved for testing to evaluate the model performance.

This study presents the development and evaluation of a predictive model for identifying postoperative complications, specifically wound infection and sepsis. The model's performance was assessed using standard classification metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis. The results demonstrate strong predictive capability, with accuracy values of 93.8% for wound infection and 94% for sepsis, indicating a high rate of correct classifications. Precision scores of 89.2% and 87.1% for wound infection and sepsis, respectively, reflect the model's effectiveness in producing reliable positive predictions while minimizing false positives. Similarly, recall values of 90.1% for wound infection and 89.6% for sepsis highlight the model's ability to correctly identify the majority of actual positive cases. The F1-scores, recorded at 90.5% for wound infection and 89.1% for sepsis, further confirm a balanced performance between precision and recall. The findings highlight the effectiveness of accurate prediction of postoperative complications using random forest approach.

Introduction:

Two third of the global population lack from the access to safe, affordable and safe surgical procedures [1]. In low and middle income countries, the limited healthcare resources lead

to the delayed treatment [2]. This may required surgical intervention and increase in healthcare resources. It continues to put the sustantial pressure on healthcare system and national economies. This limited avaiability of surgical

services increase the postoperative complications which further increase the healthcare cost and resource utilization. Furthermore, it has been observed that patients experience post operative complications may increase the expenses from 119% to 172% higher than smooth recoveries [3]. Therefore, identifying individuals with high risk of postoperative complications may decrease the morbidity rate and overall financial burden on healthcare systems.

Patients with diabetes are in high risk of postoperative complications [4]. These complications can be caused by various conditions such as infections at the surgical site or sepsis which significantly affect survival and recovery rate. In diabetic patients these risk factors increase because of delay in wound healing process. In Pakistan, 9.16% patients were diagnosed with the surgery site infection which highlights the magnitude of the problem within healthcare system [5].

Sepsis is another serious life threatening condition that result in organ failure or dysfunction. It is developed as a consequence of infection at the surgical site or from any other source [6]. The early detection of sepsis can help to prevent the disease progression and minimize healthcare expense and mortality rate.

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic disease which is divided in type 1 and type 2 [7]. The former type is life threatening in condition in which body stops to produce sufficient insulin in the body and requires external insulin injections [8]. Numerous clinical studies have demonstrated that diabetic patients are at high risk of postoperative complications [9], particularly surgical site infection and sepsis. If these conditions are not treated properly it may lead to severe consequences like amputation or death [10].

Despite the well documented relationship between diabetes and post operative infection risk, clinicals still have limited number of tools to predict the early post operative complications prior to surgery [11]. The ability to identify the risk before surgery can improve clinical decision making and helps to develop the preventive strategies.

This study aims to address this challenge by developing machine learning model based on random forest algorithm. This model will estimate the risk of surgical site infection and

sepsis in diabetic patients. The algorithm is applied on the dataset collected from local hospitals and applying data preprocessing and feature selection techniques. This can help clinicians to predict the high risk patients and implement timely preventive measure to improve surgical outcomes.

Methods

Data collection

The data has been collected from the local hospitals of Hyderabad, Sindh. The dataset contains the comprehensive information of clinical variables and demographics. The dataset consist 500 record of patients diagnosed with diabetes which contains the 20 predictive variables which are relavent to postoperative outcomes. The samples consist patients with the age of 18 to 70 years with a average of 56 years. The dataset contained the detailed demographic information, surgical procedure and preoperative labortory measurements. In the dataset, both elective surgeries and emergency cases were included with the percentage of 84% and 16% respectively. The dataset did not contain any missing value or any unbiased analysis.

Features:

A total 22 varaiables were selected based on the demographic, clinical and surgical characteristics. The baseline information has been taken from yhe demographic variables included age and sex. The clinical indicators consist the factors like admission status, types of anesthesia, discharge disposition, height and weight of the patient. Whereas, surgical features consist surgical specialty, elective or emergency surgery, duration of operation and wound classification. Other features collected were smoking status, shortness of breath, and diabetes status. These all conditions contribute to the complication to risk.

Postoperative variables consist serum albumin, serum sodium and hematocrit level [12]. These labortory test were measured 24 to 48 hours prior to surgery which provide insight to patient physiological status before the procedure.

Data preprocessing:

All the variables in the dataset were transformed into the numerical format for effective analysis

of the feature extraction. The dataset was labeled by binary encoding 0 and 1 with 0 indicating absence and 1 indicates presence of the condition [13]. This encoding was followed in smoking history (0 for non smoker, 1 for smoker), sex variable (0 for male and 1 for female), admission type (0 for inpatients, 1 for out patients), anesthesia type (0 for general and 1 for local), diabetes treatment (0 for no medication and 1 for insulin). Finally the level of contamination in the wound was encoded to represent different risk levels.

After encoding these variables the dataset was ready for the preprocessing for machine learning analysis. Figure 1 shows the workflow of the model in which dataset is cleaning and preprocessing is done. After that model evaluation is done based on the performance metrics and feature selection which than implemented in the predictive model for identification of risk of sepsis and wound infection. Finally the model is trained and tested on the random forest algorithm.

Figure 1: Workflow of the model

Model Development:

In this paper, a random forest classifier was used to develop a high performance predictive model for identifying postoperative complications in diabetic patients [14]. Random forest learning algorithm uses a bootstrap sampling method to improve the accuracy by generating multiple decision trees [15]. Each tree is trained on the different subset of data which ensure the diversity and reduces variance in predictions. The models generalization capability is enhanced by selecting a random subset of

features at the each node of tree to determine the best split. For classification, majority voting mechanism is used across the tree nodes for the final output selection which lead to more stable and accurate predictions [16]. Figure 2 shows the flowchart for random forest algorithm which starts from collecting the training data. After collection bootstrap sampling and decision trees are built and finally the prediction and aggregation based on majority voting is performed which predicts the chances of infection in diabetic patients.

Figure 2: Flowchart of random forest algorithm

Results:

The performance of the predictive model was comprehensively evaluated using a range of well-established classification metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score [17], and the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC-AUC) [18] [19]. These metrics collectively provide a multidimensional assessment of the model's effectiveness in

classifying cases of wound infection and sepsis, ensuring that both overall correctness and class-specific performance are thoroughly examined. Accuracy, which reflects the proportion of correctly classified instances among all observations, was notably high, reaching 93.8% for wound infection and 94% for sepsis. These results indicate that the model demonstrates a strong ability to correctly distinguish between

positive and negative cases across both clinical conditions.

In addition to accuracy, precision was evaluated to determine the reliability of the model's positive predictions. The model achieved precision scores of 89.2% for wound infection and 87.1% for sepsis, indicating that the majority of predicted positive cases were indeed true positives. This highlights the model's effectiveness in minimizing false positive outcomes, which is particularly critical in clinical decision-making scenarios where unnecessary interventions may result from incorrect predictions. Furthermore, recall, also referred to as sensitivity, was calculated to assess the model's ability to identify actual positive cases. The recall values of 90.1% for wound infection and 89.6% for sepsis demonstrate that the model is highly

capable of detecting true cases, thereby reducing the likelihood of missed diagnoses.

To provide a balanced measure of the model's performance, the F1-score was also considered. As the harmonic mean of precision and recall, the F1-score offers a single metric that captures both the model's ability to correctly identify positive cases and its capacity to avoid false positives. The F1-scores were recorded as 90.5% for wound infection and 89.1% for sepsis, further confirming that the model maintains a well-balanced performance across both sensitivity and specificity. A comparative analysis of these metrics, as illustrated in table 1 which shows the model performance comparison of wound infection and sepsis with respect to accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score. However, figure 3 shows the same comparison in graph representation.

Table 1: Model performance comparison in numbers

Metric	Wound Infection (%)	Sepsis (%)
Accuracy	93.8	94.0
Precision	89.2	87.1
Recall	90.1	89.6
F1-Score	90.5	89.1

Figure 3: model performance comparison

Figure 4 shows the ROC curve which illustrates the performance of predictive model for wound infections and sepsis. The curve for sepsis is slightly superior than the wound infection i.e.

AUC 0.95 and AUC 0.92 respectively. Both curves show the strong model performance in distinguishing between positive and negative cases.

Figure 4: ROC curve of wound infection and sepsis for false positive and true positive cases

Conclusion:

The proposed model demonstrated the strong and reliable performance in identifying postoperative complication with respect to wound infections and sepsis. The model uses random forest algorithm and evaluated the results on accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score. The model showed the high accuracy value of 93.8% for wound infection and 94% for sepsis which show the model capability for correctly predicting results.

Furthermore, the recall scores highlight the model's strong sensitivity in capturing the majority of actual positive cases, which is crucial in clinical applications where missing a true case can have serious consequences. The balanced F1-scores further validate the model's overall performance by effectively combining both precision and recall into a single measure. Additionally, the ROC curve analysis, with high AUC values, demonstrates the model's excellent ability to distinguish between patients with and without complications.

Overall, the results indicate that the model is both accurate and reliable, with strong generalization capability. Its ability to maintain consistent performance across different evaluation metrics makes it a valuable tool for early detection and risk assessment of wound infection and sepsis. The implementation of such a predictive system in clinical settings can support healthcare professionals in making

timely and informed decisions, ultimately improving patient outcomes, reducing complications, and optimizing resource utilization.

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